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PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

GLOBAL AND EUROPEAN INSTRUMENTS AS THE NORMATIVE BASIS FOR INCLUSION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The article analyses the development of approaches to the education of persons with special needs / disability in international legal instruments. The development of the concept of inclusive education in international documents and policies of the EU and the Bologna process has been considered.

The realization of international and European directives on inclusion implementation in national educational legislation is the part of Ukraine's integration into the European community. They considered the two levels of legal framework influencing the formation of national legislation on inclusive education within the EHEA: the international directives of global and European level on human rights; the program documents on the European educational space formation. It is noted that the legislation of most democracies takes into account the standard rules for the equal opportunities realization for persons with disabilities, which should contribute to the creation of equal living conditions among others. The development of inclusive education concept is considered as a component of international pedagogical strategy, social and economic policy as well as of higher education. This course is embodied in the global principles of accessibility, obligatoriness, equality, non-discrimination, inclusion and quality education throughout life. In accordance with these principles, the program documents on the European educational space formation focus on reflecting the diversity of Europe's population, ensuring equal opportunities for quality education; expanding universal access to higher education and supporting the capacity of underrepresented groups. The Higher School of the countries participating in the Bologna process aims to build an inclusive society based on democratic values and human rights, to promote intercultural understanding, to develop critical thinking, religious and political tolerance, to promote gender equality, civic and democratic values, and to lay the foundations for an inclusive society. The EU program documents call for the creation of inclusive and interconnected higher education systems based on cooperation between different levels of education, ensuring the flexibility of educational models, and increasing attention to career guidance and mentoring. Therefore, inclusiveness is an indisputable criterion for the quality education.

Keywords: inclusive education, higher education, persons with disabilities, persons with special educational needs, legal and regulatory framework.

Formulation of the problem. Inclusive education is one of the leading areas for the realization of equal rights of individuals to quality education and an integral part of educational reforms in Europe and all over the world. The implementation of inclusive education, based on the idea of "school for everyone" and focused on people with special needs, is accompanied by the development of international and European regulations. It aims to ensure the availability and openness of education for people regardless of health, age or financial status, to eliminate all forms and types of discrimination, to create equal opportunities for all people for receiving quality education at all levels.

The number of individuals with disabilities is growing each year in Ukraine. At the beginning of 2020 (excluding the temporarily occupied territories of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, the city of Sevastopol and part of the temporarily occupied territories in Donetsk and Luhansk regions) there were 2703.0 such persons, among which there were 163.9 thousand of children. According to the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, at the beginning of 2019, 12959 of the individuals were among the students of higher educational institutions [12, p. 57]. This highlights the problem of the public policy formation, as well as the improving and developing the regulatory framework in the field of inclusive education, in particular the higher

education, in accordance to the international and European regulations.

Recent research and publications analysis. The problem of implementation in inclusive education is devoted to pedagogical, psychological, sociological, domestic and foreign legal intelligence, concerning its various aspects: general theoretical and methodological principles of inclusive education (J. Deppeler, L. Baida, O. Zavalniuk, O. Krasiukova-Enns, T. Lorman, D. Mitchell, T. Pushkar, D. Harvey, I. Chystiakova, O. Yarska-Smyrnova and others); to the experience of Western countries, to the legal basis and specifics of the implementation of inclusive education in Ukraine (O. Bezpalko, Z. Kyianytsia, I. Komar, R. Melnyk, I. Myshchak, etc.); to the organizational and managerial aspects of inclusive education (E. Danilavichutie, N. Diatlenko, A. Kolupaieva, O. Kuzmina, S. Lytovchenko, O. Martynchuk, Y. Naida, O. Patrykeieva, L. Savchuk, N. Sofii and others); the features of integration of youth with disabilities and their access to higher education (G. Davydenko, O. Lytvynova, N. Rzhavska, I. Stadnytska L. Fedotova, M. Tchaikovskiy, etc.). The research shows that during recent decades our country has made significant progress in implementing inclusive education at all educational levels, including higher education in accordance with international obligations in the field of the rights of individuals with special educational needs.

However, *there are still unsolved various large-scale tasks* related to the further implementation of inclusion into the field of higher education: development of educational programs and training of qualified personnel to work in the context of inclusion; educational and methodological support and professional development of teachers; safe educational environment creating and ensuring its reasonable adaptation to educational needs; raising of the social status and improving the mechanisms of employment of persons with disabilities, accompanying students with special educational needs in the learning process, etc.

Solving the problems of implementation of inclusive education in Ukraine requires, as stated in the draft of "National Strategy on Development of Inclusive Education 2020-2030" [9], "the consolidation of state efforts with the involvement of public associations, charities and international organizations in cooperation with the participants of educational process". The state policy has been recognized as one of the three strategic goals for the specified period, the one that meets the educational needs of each person on the legislative and monitoring levels.

Regarding the compliance of national legislation with international norms, we should take into account the approach set out in the Law on Higher Education (2014): "if international agreements of Ukraine, the binding nature of which has been approved by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, establish the rules that differ from those provided by national legislation, the rules of international agreements shall be applied." [10]. This means that the development of national legislation on inclusive education requires not only taking into account the experience of its implementation in other countries, but also the coherence with international and European regulations recognized by Ukraine.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the development of international and European norms and standards of inclusive education.

Statement of basic material. The consolidation of human rights in legislation and the provision of appropriate guarantees in the constitutions of the vast majority of democratic countries have become, according to O. Tomali, a characteristic feature of the legal systems development of the XX century [14]. Therefore, the process of integration into the European community implies the obligation of Ukraine to implement international and European directives in the field of human rights, including persons with special educational needs and disabilities, into national legislation.

For the first time, the problems of people with disabilities were articulated on the international level by the Declaration of the Rights of the Child (1959) [4]. This document states that a physically, mentally or socially disabled child must be provided with "special treatment, education and care necessary in view of his or her special condition." Such a model of disability, which linked disabilities to human illness and considered the disability as a personal problem, is defined as medical one. Its implementation that has become widespread in many countries, has led to the isolation of people with disabilities from social processes, complicating their further socialization. The right of a child

with a disability is not to be discriminated in any area, including the exercise their right to education, is also consolidated in Articles 2 and 23 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) and in Article 29 on educational objectives.

The first practical step towards the consolidation of the international community's efforts to prevent disability, restore capacity and achieve the goals of "equality" and "full participation" of persons with disabilities in social life was the adoption of the World Program of Action Concerning Disabled Persons (1982) by the UN General Assembly [3]. The document aimed all countries to create the same living conditions for these people and to improve these conditions as a result of social and economic development. The program emphasized that the disability of a person is caused by the environment - cultural, physical or social barriers that prevent their access to various spheres of social life. This approach marked a reorientation from medical to the social model of disability, which later became the basis of the inclusive education concept.

This approach is reflected in the UN Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities (1993) [13], which consist of 22 rules aimed at equalizing opportunities for the realization of human rights for persons with disabilities. As for the education of this group of people, the priority has been defined as the form of training in "integrated structures" in ordinary schools with the provision of translation services and other appropriate support services designed to meet the needs of people with various forms of disability.

Although these rules are for guidance only, as I. Myshchak notes, the majority of democratic countries, including Ukraine, see them as a clear guideline for the development of national regulations to ensure equal opportunities for persons with disabilities, which is the legal basis for the implementation of inclusive education. [8, p. 39].

The crucial step towards the implementation of inclusive education was the adoption of the Salamanca Statement (1994) [11], which formulated a new conceptual approach to the education of people with special educational needs – the "school for all" defined guidelines for its implementation at national, regional and international levels. The notion "persons with special educational needs" included all children and young people "whose needs depend on different types of special educational needs or learning difficulties". Inclusive education has been declared a component of pedagogical strategy and new social and economic policies, and inclusive schools have been declared the most effective means of combating discrimination on the grounds of disability and the development of an inclusive society.

According to the approach declared in the Salamanca Statement, K. Kolchenko and G. Nikulina point out that inclusive education can be defined as "a system of educational services based on the principle of ensuring the basic human right to receive quality education in any chosen institution. Inclusive education in a higher educational institution (similarly with high school) can be defined as a comprehensive process of

ensuring equal access to quality higher education for students with disabilities by organizing the training taking into account the individual characteristics of their educational and cognitive activities" [5, p. 14].

The concept of inclusive education was further developed in the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006) [7]. The Convention finally emphasized that the understanding of disability is evolving, that it is the result of interactions between people with disabilities and relative and environmental barriers, which hinder the full and effective participation of persons with disabilities in public life. The Convention for the first time proclaimed a course to ensure inclusion at all levels of education and defined the tasks of States parties to ensure that disability does not lead to the exclusion of a person from the system of free and compulsory general education at the place of residence; about reasonable adaptation taking into account individual needs; on providing support within the education system for a person with a disability to facilitate his or her effective learning and on organizing individualized support for him or her. The Convention also provides persons with disabilities the equal and non-discriminatory access to higher education and vocational training, as well as the adults to education and lifelong learning, which requires the state to provide reasonable accommodation by creating the necessary conditions.

Thus, the considered international documents lay down the following principles for education: accessibility and obligation; equality, non-discrimination, inclusion; quality education.

Higher education is an influential factor in affirming the ideals of social justice in society, it is also appropriate to people with special educational needs, including people with disabilities. Although education is not the only factor in the social isolation of these people, it can promote their involvement into the full life and self-realization in society due to its multiple influences on it, as well as by stimulating changes in state policy towards people with disabilities.

Today, in the context of political, economic and social integration in Europe, higher education is undergoing significant changes. Since the late 1990s, the pace of change has reached unprecedented levels, largely because of two key processes: the adoption of the Bologna Declaration (1999), which aims to make European higher education systems more competitive and attractive, and the EU's Lisbon Strategy (2000), which aims to transform the fragmented higher education systems of the continent into a more powerful and integrated, knowledge-based economy [2].

In the context of the dissemination of inclusive education, an important document was the Communiqué of the Conference of Ministers of Education of the Bologna Process "European Higher Education Area in the New Decade" (2009) [1], held in Leuven. The preamble to the Communiqué stated that European higher education would be successful if it maximized the talents and opportunities of all its citizens; and it would be fully involved in lifelong learning and expand the social partners' participation in the higher education system. The second part of the Communiqué reveals the priorities of higher education for the period up to 2020, which, in

particular, states that students should reflect the diversity of Europe's population and provide equal opportunities for quality education. Emphasis was put on the need to support the potential of students from the groups underrepresented in higher education, to provide them with adequate learning conditions at all levels, and to "expand general access to higher education and increase access to those groups underrepresented."

At the Conference of Ministers of Education in Yerevan (2015), the state parties of the Bologna Process stated the systemic values supported by the EHEA, in which higher education would contribute to the promotion of inclusive societies based on democratic values and human rights. They declared the support of higher education institutions in their persistent efforts to promote intercultural development, critical thinking, religious and political tolerance, gender equality, civic and democratic values in order to strengthen European and global society and to establish an inclusive society [15].

This approach is followed in the "Renewed EU Agenda for Higher Education" (2017) [16] which was approved at the annual conference of national experts on higher education reform. Among the four new priorities of higher education there was the creation of inclusive and interconnected higher education systems. It is emphasized that the social groups that are least represented in higher education are often less prepared for it; therefore, the cooperation between different levels of education is needed to prepare and guide the students basing on their talents rather than their experience, and to ensure flexible models for education and training. The emphasis is put on the exceptional importance of career guidance and mentoring.

Thus, the comparison of the EU policy documents and the Bologna Process suggests that, in both approaches, the inclusiveness of higher education is an indisputable priority and an important criterion for the quality of education.

Conclusions. Education, including higher education, is a leading means of social protection and social inclusion development of people with special needs / disabilities. International directives of two levels: global and European, are the normative legal basis for the formation of national legislation in the field of inclusive education in Ukraine within the EHEA. The former include major international human rights instruments developed and approved by specialized agencies and the UN agencies (UNESCO, the International Labor Organization, the World Health Organization, etc.). The second level documents include, first of all, the program documents of the EU and the Bologna Process.

Since its independence, Ukraine has committed itself to respecting universal human rights, in particular to ensuring the right to higher education for people with special educational needs in accordance with international norms and standards. By ratifying the Lisbon Convention and acceding to the Bologna Declaration, Ukraine must also adhere to the strategic priority of ensuring equality and social cooperation in the framework of European cooperation in education. This needs further development and improvement in accordance with

world and European standards of the legal framework focused on inclusive education implementation at all levels of education in Ukraine.

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PREPARING STUDENTS FOR C1 BUSINESS HIGHER WRITING PARTS 1 AND 2

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Abstract:

The following paper is aimed at developing students' BEC Higher writing skills. "Teaching exam classes" specialism is believed to be rather challenging and at the same time extremely rewarding to teach, think and write about, especially if you want to bring this process to a new level. Currently, I am teaching 11 second-year students who are going to take the "C1 Business Higher" exam this summer. This exam is included in the students' educational program because it is accepted by many Russian and European universities if one wants to enroll in a master's degree program. Moreover, many companies trust Cambridge assessment quality knowing that the test results are trustworthy.

Keywords: motivation, C1 Business Higher exam, syllabus writing, sequencing, examination classes, formative/summative assessment, testing vs teaching

Part 1

Examination classes versus General English classes (GE)

Teaching an exam class has its peculiar features that will be different from teaching a GE class. For instance, while preparing for an exam, students are united by the mutual goal (May, 1996: 4) to pass the exam suc-